

Event metadata

Event title	No code, no problem - data analysis for biologists with Galaxy Australia
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	29/04/2025
Time of event	12pm AEST
Topic description	<p>Life science research is all about data. Turning that data into useful biological knowledge and publication-worthy figures requires specialised bioinformatics resources and compute. This is where Galaxy comes in.</p> <p>Galaxy is an accessible, online platform for reproducible and transparent data analysis. You don't need command line skills to use it and it includes 1000's of popular, community backed bioinformatics tools which is why it has become the go-to platform for thousands of life scientists worldwide.</p> <p>Join us to learn how Galaxy is being used in a wide range of research including genome assembly and annotation, metagenomics, proteomics, transcriptomics, data visualisation and more. We'll show you the features that make this such a versatile platform whether you are new to data analysis or are looking to take your workflows to the next level!</p> <p>Galaxy Australia is a fully subsidised service provided by Australian BioCommons.</p> <p>The service receives NCRIS funding through Bioplatforms Australia, as well as The University of Melbourne and Queensland Government RICF funding.</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/galaxy-webinar-2025
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless

	otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Data analysis http://edamontology.org/operation_2945
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This webinar is for life scientists and bioinformaticians who need to analyse and interpret biological data. New and experienced data analysts are welcome.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	By the end of this webinar you should be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe how Galaxy Australia has been used to aid research • Describe the layout of the Galaxy Australia interface • Outline tools and resources available in Galaxy Australia • Outline the features of Galaxy Australia that support reproducible research • Identify sources of help, support and further training
Speakers	Dr Tiffanie Nelson, Genomics Research Community Engagement Lead, Australian BioCommons Dr Tristan Reynolds, Galaxy Outreach Specialist, The University of Melbourne
Training materials	Materials shared in this Zenodo record: Slides presented during the webinar: 2025-04-29 No code no problem - data analysis with Galaxy.pdf Materials shared elsewhere: A recording of this webinar is available on the Australian BioCommons YouTube Channel: https://youtu.be/XGGbCzhFIFl
Related material	None